

90 YEARS OF SILENCE

RECONSTRUCTING, RETURNING, REACTIVATING A SOUND ARCHIVE OF THE HORN OF AFRICA

“90 Years of Silence” tells the story of a dispersed collection: a sound heritage recomposed through collective research, curation, and digitisation, transforming fragmented memories into a shared experience.

During the Italian occupation of Ethiopia (1936-1941), on the eve of Second World War, about 350 recordings of traditional music were produced in Addis Ababa, capturing a remarkable range of musical forms and instrumentation. This ambitious undertaking involved, among other labels, the Italian branch of Columbia Records, and proceeded under military supervision.

The recordings were intended for commercial release, but the project was halted by the outbreak of war. A handful of promotional copies survived in mixed circumstances: some entered private collections, others resurfaced in antique shops, and many were abandoned in dusty rooms.

No institution preserved the collection in its entirety. Recently identified documents at the Biblioteca IsIAO (now held at the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Rome) indicate an attempt to establish a “Discoteca coloniale” (colonial sound archive) that once contained about 100 records, of which only 28 survive. The Istituto Centrale per i Beni Sonori e Audiovisivi, the former Discoteca di Stato (national sound archive) also holds approximately twenty related discs.

Through collective research and archival retrieval, nearly 300 recordings produced by different record labels have been collected. They have been traced, digitised, and catalogued, then returned as a digital collection to the National Archives and Library Agency - Ethiopia’s national archive. This shared, multi-stage process fills a historical gap. It also included transcription and translation of texts and, for selected items, sound restoration.

Reconstructing this sound archive does not conclude the journey of these recordings; it renews it. On the one hand, it reactivates them by recirculating a cultural heritage of extraordinary breadth and complexity. On the other hand, it raises new questions about the biographies of the musicians whose voices and sounds were captured, and about the conditions of recording under an imperial regime imposed less than a century ago.

The exhibition - through a multisensory path of explanatory panels, visual materials, audio content, and reconstructions of the 78 rpm discs that preserved these sounds - seeks both to restore access and to provide critical context.

The endeavor of documenting musical expressions took place within a system of violence and under the strict control of Italian officials - the same authorities who, during the 1937 campaign against perceived enemies, imprisoned and killed *azmariwočč* and other musicians. “90 Years of Silence” acknowledges how occupation silenced many artists, even as it selectively documented some when deemed opportune.

As a result, the recordings belong to a broader, Eurocentric history of documenting music worldwide - aligned with practices of recording, cataloguing, and circulating sounds that accompanied imperial projects. However, they are also part of the Horn of Africa’s long and layered history of cultural production. They can therefore be recognised as expressions of living, dynamic, and far from marginal musical traditions.

The exhibition interrogates the role of sound collections when they return to the public sphere. Archives are not neutral repositories; they are devices that can reactivate memories, responsibilities, and sometimes conflicting narratives. When made accessible, they can fuel critical reflection on the legacies of cultural operations that served regimes of power. At the same time, this process restores dignity and visibility to the professionals - often left anonymous or only faintly sketched - by recognising them as historical subjects and bearers of specific musical knowledge, whose voices continue to resonate in the present.

THE QR CODES ARE A KEY PART OF THE EXHIBITION: BY SCANNING THEM, YOU CAN HEAR THE RECORDINGS, LEARN MORE ABOUT THE SOUND ARCHIVE, AND ACCESS TRANSLATIONS OF THE PANELS.

ITALIAN COLONIALISM IN AFRICA: ORIGINS, PHASES AND LEGACIES

Italian colonialism in Africa formed part of a broader, long-term transformation that, between the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, saw the erosion of African independence and its replacement by European occupation and colonial rule. Across the continent, imperial expansion was pursued through diplomacy, coercion and open violence, and justified through the rhetoric of the “three Cs”: Commerce, Civilisation and Christianity. These processes profoundly reshaped Africa’s political structures, economic systems and social relations.

In the Italian case, colonial expansion began informally in 1869 with the purchase of ‘Asäb Bay by the Rubattino Shipping Company. In 1882, ‘Asäb was taken over by the Italian state, marking the transition from private initiative to formal colonial policy. From there, Italy expanded its presence in the Horn of Africa, consolidating control in Eritrea and establishing its position in Somalia through agreements, protectorates and military intervention. At the same time, it sought to extend its influence over Ethiopia, but these ambitions met determined resistance and resulted in major defeats, most notably at ‘Adwa in 1896. Italy’s colonial project later extended to North Africa with the Italo-Turkish War of 1911-1912, which led to the occupation of Tripolitania and Cyrenaica.

This history can be read through four broad phases: informal colonialism (1869-1882); Liberal colonialism (1882-1922); Fascist colonialism (1922-1943); and the so-called Republican colonialism, which followed the formal end of empire. These phases reveal both continuity and rupture in the ways territories were occupied, governed and represented. Administrative methods changed, as did the scale of violence, segregation and ideological control, yet important continuities remained in the unequal structures of power created by colonial domination.

In every colonial territory, African actors were never passive subjects. Italian rule was shaped not only by military conquest and administrative control, but also by African collaboration, negotiation, adaptation and resistance. These responses took many forms and often coexisted, reminding us that colonial history was never one-sided, but always the outcome of unequal and contested encounters.

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ITALY AND ETHIOPIA: A CONTESTED IMPERIAL PROJECT

For decades, Italian expansionist ambitions were directed towards Ethiopia, a multilingual, multi-confessional and politically complex empire that stood out in Africa for its ability to preserve its sovereignty against European encroachment. From the liberal age to the fascist one, Italy's designs on Ethiopia revealed both the continuity of colonial ambition and the limits of Italian power. These ambitions met with decisive resistance under the *nəguś* Mənilək II, whose military and diplomatic leadership culminated in the Ethiopian victory at the Battle of 'Adwa in 1896. More than a military defeat for Italy, 'Adwa became a symbol of the failure of European imperial claims before an African state capable of defending its independence on the battlefield as well as at the negotiating table. Its significance remains profound to this day: 'Adwa is still celebrated as a national holiday in Ethiopia, standing as a lasting emblem of sovereignty, anti-colonial resistance and national unity. In the twentieth century, Mənilək's legacy was carried forward by *ətege* Zāwditu and later by *nəguś* Ḥaylā Śəllase, who combined negotiation, international diplomacy and internal statecraft to preserve Ethiopian independence in the face of renewed foreign pressure.

Under Fascism, Italy's long-standing ambition to control Ethiopia became a project of imperial expansion. The invasion of 1935-1936 was driven by

the desire to avenge the defeat at 'Adwa by confidence in Italy's military superiority, by the then prime minister Benito Mussolini's need to recover prestige after the economic crisis triggered by the Wall Street Crash, and the regime's claim that Italians needed new land for work and settlement. In reality, this was less a matter of population pressure than of political ambition and imperial ideology.

On 3 October 1935, Italy invaded Ethiopia, a sovereign state and a member of the League of Nations. Ḥaylā Śəllase denounced the aggression before the League of Nations, whose response was limited to economic sanctions that proved ineffective. Colonial and Italian troops entered Addis Ababa on 5 May 1936; four days later, on 9 May, Mussolini proclaimed the the birth of the Africa Orientale Italiana - AOI (Italian East Africa), the new imperial entity that united Eritrea, Ethiopia and Somalia under Italian rule from 1936 to 1941. Yet occupation remained in many areas more formal than real. Across the country, the *arbāññočč* - the Ethiopian patriots - organised armed resistance, drawing support from regional elites, peasants, urban networks

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and members of the Orthodox Church. The Church was a force that helped sustain anti-occupation sentiment, offered moral legitimacy to resistance and, for this reason, became a target of repression.

Violence was central to Fascist rule in Ethiopia. Italy used mustard gas despite being party to the 1925 Geneva Protocol prohibiting chemical warfare. Repression reached a turning point after the attack on Viceroy Rodolfo Graziani on 19 February 1937, carried out by Abreha Däboč and Mogäs Asgädom. The Italian response culminated in mass reprisals in Addis Ababa and, soon after, in the massacre of Däbrä Libanos, executed by troops under General Pietro Maletti on Graziani's orders.

This was also the phase in which racism became fully institutionalised through the racial laws in the late 1930s and the early 1940s. In the name of the "prestige of race", Fascist authorities introduced measures designed to segregate Italians and Africans, restrict contact, and prevent *madamismo* - the widespread practice whereby Italian men entered into intimate and sexual relationships of concubinage with African women - and *meticciato*, that is, the birth of mixed-ancestry children, who were often referred to by derogatory names. These policies, however, formed part of a wider imperial design that sought to involve the masses in the imperial enterprise and to cultivate among them a specifically imperial consciousness. At the same time, the empire had to be made visible: its territories were to be exhibited, valued, and represented as tangible expressions of national power and as the product of Italian labour, conquest, and settlement. It is within this broader representational and media framework of Italian colonialism that the recording campaign should be situated.

As the exhibition "90 Years of Silence" makes clear, these recordings

belonged to a wider soundscape of the colonial experience, linked to practices of recording, cataloguing, and circulating sounds that accompanied the imperial project and contributed to making the Horn of Africa available to metropolitan perception and imagination.

TIMELINE

INFORMAL PHASE

- > **15 NOVEMBER 1869** Giuseppe Sapeto, acting for the Rubattino Company, signed the contract for the purchase of 'Asāb Bay with the chiefs Hasan and Ibrāhīm b. Aḥmad, who presented themselves as sultans of Raḥayta, usually taken as the starting point of Italian colonial expansion in the Horn of Africa.
- > **11 MARCH 1870** The 'Asāb purchase was ratified. Italian presence on the Red Sea remains dependent on negotiation with local rulers and regional balances of power.
- > **1881** Muḥammad Aḥmad proclaimed himself the *mahdī* in Sudan, inaugurating the Mahdist uprising; the movement soon became a major regional force and helped shape the strategic context of Italian expansion in the region.

LIBERAL PHASE

- > **5 JULY 1882** The Italian state formally took over 'Asāb from Rubattino, turning a private foothold into a state colonial possession.
- > **26 APRIL - 16 NOVEMBER 1884** At the Esposizione Generale Italiana in Turin, 'Asāb was publicly displayed, marking an early moment in the exhibition and popularisation of Italy's presence in Africa.
- > **15 NOVEMBER 1884 - 26 FEBRUARY 1885** The Berlin Conference established the rules of the European scramble for Africa: it sought to regulate imperial competition, guarantee free trade and navigation in the Congo and Niger regions, and legitimise territorial claims through the principle of effective occupation. No African representatives took part.
- > **5 FEBRUARY 1885** Italy occupies Massawa, expanding inland from the coast into an area contested by Ethiopian, Egyptian, and local forces.
- > **JULY 1885** Kassala fell to the Mahdists, marking the expansion of Mahdist power towards the Eritrean frontier and becoming an important element in the regional context of early Italian colonial consolidation.
- > **26 JANUARY 1887** At Dog'ali, Ethiopian forces defeated an Italian column, an early and decisive sign that African resistance was central to the history of Italian expansion.
- > **7 AUGUST 1887** Francesco Crispi became Prime Minister; from this point, colonial expansion in the Horn of Africa assumed a more central and assertive role in Italian foreign policy.
- > **1887** The first Eritrean colonial troops are regularised by General Antonio Baldissera, marking the formal organisation of indigenous troops in Italian colonial service.
- > **1888** The crisis later known as the *kəfu qān* began in northern Ethiopia and developed into the Great Famine of 1888-1892.
- > **1889** Formation of the first four Eritrean battalions, thereafter known as *ascari*.
- > **1889** Italy began to acquire protectorates in southern Somalia through treaties with the sultanates of Hobyo and Maḡeerteen, extending its influence beyond the Benaadir coast.
- > **2 MAY 1889** Count Pietro Antonelli, for Italy, and *nəguś* Mənilək II signed the Treaty of Wačale. While the treaty recognised Italian occupation of Eritrea, the conflicting wording of Article 17 allowed Italy to claim a protectorate over Ethiopia, a reading Mənilək rejected and which later became a major cause of tensions.
- > **1 JANUARY 1890** Italy proclaimed the colony of Eritrea its *colonia primigenia*.
- > **1893** The Filonardi Company began administering the Somali territories under Italian protection, inaugurating a phase of indirect colonial control.
- > **17 JULY 1894** At the Battle of Kassala, Italian colonial forces under Oreste Baratieri defeated Mahdist Sudanese troops and occupied the town, which remained under Italian control until 1897.
- > **DECEMBER 1894** Bahta Ḥagos led an anti-Italian resistance in Akkälä Guzay; he was killed at Ḥalay, on 19 December 1894.
- > **1 MARCH 1896** At 'Adwa, Ethiopia defeated Italy; *nəguś* Mənilək II preserved Ethiopian sovereignty and reshaped the limits of European colonial power in the Horn of Africa.
- > **16 JULY 1896** The administration of the Benaadir was formally handed over to Italy, consolidating Italian control on the Somali coast.
- > **1903** Giovanni Giolitti returned to office as Prime Minister, inaugurating a phase in which liberal Italy combined limited mass integration at home with renewed colonial ambitions abroad.
- > **1904** The Museo Coloniale was established in Rome as a museum intended to collect, display, and popularise materials from the Italian colonies for a metropolitan public.
- > **1904** The Istituto Agricolo Coloniale Italiano was founded in Florence; it was the institution later known as the Istituto Agronomico per l'Oltremare. Its original purpose was to promote the study of tropical environments and agriculture and to train technical personnel for the agricultural exploitation of the colonies.
- > **14 APRIL 1905** Italy placed Benaadir under direct sovereignty, transforming the earlier lease and company administration into direct colonial rule.
- > **SEPTEMBER-OCTOBER 1905** The First Italian Colonial Congress was held in Asmara, a key moment in the consolidation of pro-colonial networks and in the public elaboration of Italy's colonial project.
- > **1906** The Istituto Coloniale Italiano was founded in Rome, as a centre for colonial studies, propaganda, publications, and the coordination of pro-colonial networks.
- > **5 APRIL 1908** The Colony of Italian Somaliland was formally constituted, completing the earlier process of acquisition and administrative consolidation.
- > **29 APRIL-19 NOVEMBER 1911** At the Turin International Exhibition, Italy mounted colonial displays including exhibits on Eritrea and Italian Somaliland.

- > **29 SEPTEMBER 1911** Italy declared war on the Ottoman Empire in order to seize Tripolitania and Cyrenaica. Ottoman and local resistance began immediately.
- > **18 OCTOBER 1912** The Treaty of Ouchy (Lausanne) ended the Italo-Turkish War; the Ottoman Empire renounced Tripolitania and Cyrenaica, though Italian control on the ground remained partial and contested.

FASCIST PHASE

- > **28-30 OCTOBER 1922** The March on Rome marked the Fascist seizure of power and Benito Mussolini was appointed Prime Minister.
- > **1923** The Fascist "pacification" of Libya intensified, especially in Cyrenaica, through large-scale repression, forced displacement, concentration camps, and counter-insurgency warfare.
- > **3 JANUARY 1925** Mussolini openly assumed political responsibility for Fascist violence before Parliament, a key moment in the transition from authoritarian government to dictatorship.
- > **2 NOVEMBER 1930** Ras Tāfāri Mäkwännən was proclaimed Emperor of Ethiopia, taking the name *nəguś* Ḥaylā Šəllase I.
- > **16 SEPTEMBER 1931** Umar al-Muḥṭār, the most prominent leader of the anti-Italian resistance in Cyrenaica, was executed by the Italians near Sulūq, marking a decisive moment in the crushing of organised resistance in Cyrenaica.
- > **OCTOBER 1934** Naples hosted the Seconda Mostra internazionale d'arte coloniale.
- > **3 DECEMBER 1934** With Regio Decreto Legge n. 2012, Italy reorganised its North African possessions as the colony of Libya, unifying Tripolitania, Cyrenaica, and Fezzan under a single colonial framework.
- > **5 DECEMBER 1934** The Wälwāl incident became the immediate pretext for the invasion of Ethiopia.
- > **3 OCTOBER 1935** Italy invaded Ethiopia.
- > **7 OCTOBER - 18 NOVEMBER 1935** The League of Nations Council formally declared that Italy has resorted to war in violation of Article 12 of the Covenant, and economic sanctions entered into force, including restrictions on loans and financial dealings and a ban on the export to Italy of a range of goods; the measures were later widened, though crucially without an oil embargo or the closure of the Suez Canal.
- > **9 DECEMBER 1935** Ethiopian Minister of War Mulugeta Yəggāzu called on northern chiefs to organise patriotic resistance; this is an early step in the formation of the organised anti-Italian resistance later known as the *arbāññocč*.
- > **13 FEBRUARY 1936** Gondrand massacre: Ethiopian patriots attacked the Gondrand construction site at May Lahlah, killing most of the Italian and Eritrean workers there.
- > **9 MAY 1936** Italy formally established Africa Orientale Italiana (AOI), uniting Eritrea, Ethiopia, and Italian Somaliland under one imperial structure.
- > **12 MAY 1936** *Nəguś* Ḥaylā Šəllase addressed the League of Nations in Geneva, denouncing Italian aggression and the use of chemical weapons.
- > **3 JUNE 1936** *Nəguś* Ḥaylā Šəllase and part of the Ethiopian imperial court arrived in Britain, beginning the Emperor's exile in the United Kingdom.
- > **1936** Ethiopian resistance reorganised after the fall of Addis Ababa: the *arbāññocč* took a more coherent shape, while the Black Lions - a clandestine nationalist organisation made up largely of educated young Ethiopians, including students and intellectuals close to the imperial state - attempted to give the struggle political as well as military direction.
- > **19 FEBRUARY 1937** Attempted assassination of Rodolfo Graziani in Addis Ababa by the Eritrean anti-colonial militants Abreha Däboč and Mogās Asgädom; the reprisals began immediately.
- > **19-21 FEBRUARY 1937** 12 Yakkatit Addis Ababa massacre. Italian troops, Blackshirts, and settlers carried out mass reprisals against Ethiopian civilians.
- > **1937** After 12 Yakkatit, the occupation intensified deportations and internment: colonial subjects were sent to Dhanaane in Somalia and to the penal colony of Nokra in Eritrea; deportations to confinement sites in Italy, including Asinara and Longobucco, began in this phase and continued into 1939.
- > **19 APRIL 1937** Regio Decreto Legge n. 880, Sanzioni per i rapporti d'indole coniugale fra cittadini e sudditi: the first major racial law in the colonial sphere, criminalising more uxorio mixed unions between Italians and colonial subjects.
- > **SUMMER-AUTUMN 1937** The Ethiopian resistance became more regionally organised: revolts spread in Lasta, Bägəmdər, Goḡgam, and Šāwa under leaders including Abbäbä Arägay, Bälay Zälläqä, and Ḥaylu Käbbädä.
- > **30 DECEMBER 1937** Law n. 2590 converted and modified Regio Decreto Legge 880, consolidating the ban on intimate and marital relations between Italians and colonial subjects.
- > **17 NOVEMBER 1938** Regio Decreto Legge n. 1728, Provvedimenti per la difesa della razza italiana extended the racial turn at the metropolitan level; colonial racism and anti-Jewish racism now form part of one legal and ideological framework.
- > **5 JANUARY 1939** Law n. 274 converted Regio Decreto Legge 1728 into law.
- > **29 JUNE 1939** Law n. 1004, *Sanzioni penali per la difesa del prestigio di razza di fronte ai nativi dell'Africa Italiana*: another key colonial racial law, explicitly linking criminal sanctions to the defence of racial prestige.
- > **1939** The large-scale recording campaign at the centre of "90 Years of Silence" takes place in Addis Ababa: the collection under the auspices of Columbia Records produced more than two hundred recordings before the war interrupted their intended commercial release.

- > **9 MAY 1940** Opening of the *Prima Mostra Triennale delle Terre Italiane d'Oltremare* in Naples, conceived as a major display of imperial space, labour, resources, and prestige; it was intended to run until 15 October 1940.
- > **JUNE 1940** Italy's entry into the Second World War effectively curtailed the Naples exhibition after about a month.
- > **5 MAY 1941** *Nəguś* Ḥaylā Šəllase returned to Addis Ababa, accompanied by British forces and Ethiopian patriots.
- > **25 FEBRUARY 1941** The British Military Administration began in Eritrea.
- > **NOVEMBER 1941** Collapse of Italian East Africa.
- > **25 JULY 1943** Fall of Fascism: Mussolini was dismissed and arrested.
- > **8 SEPTEMBER 1943** The armistice was announced; German occupation and the Italian civil war began.

REPUBLICAN PHASE

- > **2 JUNE 1946** Italy voted for the republic in the institutional referendum.
- > **3 JULY 1946** The Council of Foreign Ministers adopted the framework that led to international discussion of the fate of the former Italian colonies.
- > **12 NOVEMBER 1947 | 3 JANUARY 1948** The Four-Power Commission of Investigation for the former Italian colonies visited Eritrea.
- > **MAY 1949** The Bevin-Storza plan was negotiated; it proposed a partition-based solution for the former Italian colonies but failed to secure approval.
- > **21 NOVEMBER 1949** UN General Assembly Resolution 289 (IV) decided for the independence of Libya, Eritrea and Ethiopia Federation, and Somalia to be placed under trusteeship.
- > **1 APRIL 1950** Italy assumed the trusteeship administration of Somalia (AFIS).
- > **2 DECEMBER 1950** UN General Assembly Resolution 390 A (V) provided for the federation of Eritrea with Ethiopia.
- > **1952** The Comitato per la documentazione dell'opera dell'Italia in Africa is established in connection with the planned suppression of the Ministry of Italian Africa, in order to preserve, organise, and publish an official documentary record of Italy's presence in Africa through the series *L'Italia in Africa*.
- > **15 SEPTEMBER 1952** The British Administration ended in Eritrea and the Federation of Eritrea and Ethiopia came into force.
- > **29 APRIL 1953** Law n. 430, *Soppressione del Ministero dell'Africa italiana* abolished the Ministry of Italian Africa.
- > **1955** The first volumes of *L'Italia in Africa* began to appear under Comitato's supervision, to document and reframe Italy's African past.
- > **1 JULY 1960** The AFIS came to an end with the independence of Somalia and its union with former British Somaliland in the Somali Republic.
- > **13 DECEMBER 1960** Failed coup attempt against the *nəguś* Ḥaylā Šəllase led by Brigadier General Mängästu Neway and Germame Neway.
- > **1 SEPTEMBER 1961** The Eritrean liberation struggle began, when Ḥämüd Idrīs 'Awate and his companions launch the first armed action at 'Adal, inaugurating the long anti-Ethiopian campaign.
- > **14 NOVEMBER 1962** Ḥaylā Šəllase unilaterally dissolved the Federation and annexed Eritrea as the fourteenth province of the Ethiopian Empire, bringing Eritrea's autonomous status formally to an end.

THE MUSICAL CONTEXT

One of the principal forces shaping the development of music in Ethiopia has been the Orthodox Church. The hymns attributed to *qəddus* Yared (Saint Yared) constitute a centuries-old record of *zema* (religious chant) that still resonates today in churches and monasteries. The indigenous notational system, besides preserving the tradition, favoured the organisation of sacred chant into modes. This modal framework subsequently influenced secular music as well, where the modes crystallised into four musical scales, named *qəññət*. These correspond to distinct expressive modalities and specific sentiments, and they underpin much of modern and musical practices. The names of the four secular modes are *təzzəta*, *bati*, *ančihoy*, and *ambassäl*. Drawing on the so-called Checchia collection, Francis Falceto and Stephanie Weisser studied early uses of these modes in secular repertoires. They determined that the terms *bati* and *ančihoy* were already in circulation in the 1930s, whereas *təzzəta* and *ambassäl* appear to be more recent elaborations.

The *azmari* (pl. *azmariwočč*) - storyteller, musician, author, and performer of oral poetry - is a figure with deep historical roots. As Simeneh Betreyohannes Gebremariam recounts, although they cultivated ties with the Church and political authority, *azmariwočč* have long maintained a remarkable expressive freedom that has been both admired and feared. In urban contexts, *az-*

mariwočč performed in *azmari bet* - venues for gathering and performance - where news and commentary circulated swiftly and reached communities. This communicative power was particularly feared by the occupying forces. At the same time, the Italian authorities decided to allow many of these performances to be recorded. The recordings in the Checchia collection together with other contemporary collections - though not the earliest historical recordings of *azmariwočč* - offer an extraordinary panoramic view of the creativity and sound world that characterised the period.

Like other musical traditions worldwide, the music of the Horn of Africa has evolved through contact with other musical languages, particularly Western music. Bowed strings and numerous brass instruments entered the country via Christian missions or as gifts from rulers and allies. Historically, a pivotal moment in this encounter is identified with the arrival in 1924 of forty Armenian orphans, whom *ras* Täfäri Mäkwännən (the future *nəguś* Ḥaylä Šəllase) invited to Addis Ababa. These forty young musicians, the so-called *Arba Ləgočč*, would form the core of the first imperial orchestra.

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A central element of musical poetics is the verbal practice of wax and gold (*sāmenna wārq*). The expression encapsulates the idea that a surface meaning (the wax) conceals a deeper, more precious meaning, the gold, accessible only to those who hold the keys to its decoding. An example of this expressive technique is the song „Anči ləǧ, recorded in several versions within the Checchia collection and accessible via QR code. The history of this piece is particularly compelling, as recounted with precision by Sylvia Pankhurst:

“Traditionally, the secular songs were seldom preserved in writing, despite the existence of ancient script for recording both words and music”, explained the British writer and anti-fascist activist, who was an indefatigable campaigner for Ethiopian independence, “but if a song appealed to the sentiment of the people it could become virtually permanent by transmission from generation to generation. Moreover, though many songs have merely a local existence some spread throughout the province, and extending to the whole country may become part of the national heritage of song. One may instance the popular and tuneful [Anči ləǧ]. Composed during the sad days of the Italian occupation, it symbolizes the Ethiopian motherland as every Ethiopian was aware.”

“The song praises the beauty and delicacy of a maiden symbolizing Ethio-

pia; it runs: ‘Oh beautiful maiden, oh beautiful maiden, you are delicate and slender as a fine shamma ...’ This is the refrain. The song is then continued in impromptu rhymed verses thrown in by the singers or members of the audience containing witty innuendoes and sparkling phrases.

In several exchanges between the Ufficio Politico (Political Office) and officials outside Addis Ababa, dating to 1937, the director of the Office, Colonel Aldo Princivalle - a figure who played an important role both in recognising the cultural significance of the *azmariwočč* and in their subsequent persecution - warned about the circulation of an anti-Italian song whose title was said to be “Schiava di Etiopia” (Slave of Ethiopia), elsewhere referred to as “Slave Ethiopia” (Slave Ethiopia). Even though it is possible that Princivalle was referring to a song that already existed, we do not know of any recording of a song with this title at that time. In any case, the specific alarm subsided and did not extend to a song like “Anči ləǧ.” The Italian authorities - unable to grasp the expressive richness of wax and gold - allowed the piece to circulate and become part of the cultural heritage that these recordings have preserved until today.

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THE EXOTIC SOUND

The recordings presented here fed a demand for “exoticism” and a representation of the exotic that was particularly strong in Italy at the time. Many forces contributed to the construction of a distant imaginary: exhibitions, literature, the publication of newspapers and magazines that discussed the colonies, the film materials collected by the Istituto Luce, and radio. Such imaginary, on the one hand, established a divide between the “we” of the Italian people and the “they” of the occupied peoples. On the other hand, it created a platform for encounters and - perhaps more importantly - the possibility of documenting certain aspects of life and cultural expressions of the period.

An earlier and better known example of this kind of recording of the Other is the Berliner Phonogramm-Archiv. During the First World War, a group of scholars seeking to document and study the world’s languages and cultures from a comparative perspective recorded prisoners of war from other European countries and different continents. That body of documentation is widely studied today and has been presented in publications and exhibitions. Although civil servants and scholars such as Carlo Conti Rossini had certainly supported their production in some way, the recordings presented

here were not part of a scientific archive. Rather, they constituted a sonic survey of the musical “exotic” of the Horn of Africa, produced for use in the media and fixed primarily on 78 rpm shellac records.

In this context, the construction of a sonic imaginary should be understood through a transmedial lens - that is, through the interaction of multiple media working together to build an articulated and complex imaginary. Despite the ideological, technological, and ethical limitations embodied by the individuals and institutions involved in the collecting, these recordings return to us the fascinating sonic component of that articulation and complexity.

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THE CHECCHIA COLLECTION

Among collectors and enthusiasts, the *corpus* is known as the Checchia collection, although no contemporary source employs this term. It comprises 248 recordings drawn from various regions and traditions of the Horn of Africa. Some items are authored compositions, others belong to popular repertoires; in many cases they are versions shaped by the specific socio-political context of the period. The initiative was promoted by the Italian branch of Columbia. Records in this collection are recognisable by their trilingual sleeves - a product conceived for a global, multilingual market.

The musicologist Guglielmo Barblan, in his book *Musiche e strumenti musicali dell'Africa Orientale Italiana*, described it as "the most coherent, comprehensive, and trustworthy anthology, indispensable for anyone who wishes, from a distance, to gain a notion of Ethiopian popular lyrical art." At the same time, he noted that in 1941, the year the book was published in Italy - by which point Italian territories in the Horn of Africa had already been lost - only one of the discs had actually been released. This was disc A.I. 602, containing two Tigrinya pieces: "Canzone Massè, Lode ai capi eritrei,"

performed by Tämälso Qälätä (reported as Temelsò Chelete) with choral accompaniment, and "Storia del Cantiba Bechit," featuring the voice and *kərar* of Fəqräsəllase 'Uqbazgi (reported as Fecreselassiè Oglasghi). According to Barblan, the release occurred "at the suggestion and on the recommendation of the Mostra Triennale d'Oltremare," the massive colonial exhibition inaugurated in Naples in 1940 and closed after only one month due to Italy's entry into the Second World War. This detail suggests that the Checchia collection was conceived as a crucial sonic component in constructing the exotic imaginary associated with the Italian colonial experience.

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The choice of recorded songs - offering a diverse and substantial panorama of regional expressions from the Horn of Africa - was, according to Barblan, the outcome of a competition that saw "the most renowned minstrels of the empire" as participants. A judging commission was also involved. Indeed, the artists who converged on Ethiopia's capital were among the most accomplished and widely recognised performers. Little is known about how the competition was conducted. The photograph presented here may in fact be related to activities connected to the competition.

Overseeing the entire project was a wealthy *muwallad* merchant whose portrait appears on all the record sleeves. His name was Sa'īd Šalāḥ Aḥmad Kekkiya paša (often reported as Said Saled Ahmed Checchia Pasha), born in Massawa in 1904 to an Eritrean mother and a Yemeni father. From 1935 onward he is documented in Ethiopia, where he enjoyed considerable commercial success. Between 1938 and 1941, he received numerous commendations from the Italian authorities, including the title of Commander of the Order of the Crown of Italy. At the same time, he was kept under surveillance by those authorities, as evidenced by the existence of a police file in his name. Subsequently, Kekkiya assumed a political role within the Maḥbār faqri hagär, the Eritrean Unionist Party.

THE DIGITAL ARCHIVE

In the absence of preservation within institutional sound archives, the records from the Columbia collection and other labels each followed an independent trajectory. They have changed hands; they have spent years in basements and shops. They have been bought and sold, in person and online. Assembling all surviving discs exceeded the framework and the ambition of the research project SONIETHIO and of its restitution endeavour. Therefore, the work focused on compiling a digital archive that is as comprehensive as possible.

Given the volatile and private nature of the surviving materials - and the value of the objects that have endured over time - building the digital archive required contributions from many individuals working in diverse contexts and with different tools. Under ideal conditions, the discs were digitised using turntables equipped with a mono needle suitable for 78 rpm records, and captured in high-quality formats. The sleeves and sides were then photographed and catalogued. Not in every case, however, was it possible to maintain this high standard. The research collective will continue to improve the quality of

the files already in its possession and to expand the archive, should discs that have not yet been digitised come to light.

SOUND RESTORATION

A selected number of files underwent audio restoration with the aim of improving listening quality while preserving the original musical elements. This is a complex undertaking that faces several challenges.

A first issue concerns the noise: a sound restorer strives to select and isolate a portion within the overall sonic field, mentally reconstructing a virtual image of the musical artifact. Everything else is treated as noise. Yet, on reflection, noise is more complex. It is not simply something superimposed on the sound. The groove of a disc wears down little by little with each play.

Over time, chemical reactions from prolonged contact with environmental elements further erode it. All of this tells a story of a journey: the object in our hands documents not only the moment of its crea-

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tion, but also all the phases that have unfolded between that moment and the present.

Restoring an early disc, much like translating a text from another era, presents a temporal paradox: should we recover the listening experience of the past, or adapt the recording to contemporary aesthetic and technological standards? This also entails taking a stance: which listening vantage point should be privileged in restoration? Is it possible that our choice might, in some way, perpetuate the logics and power imbalances within which these recordings were made?

THE ACOUSTIC SPACE

Sound engineers devote considerable effort to constructing a spatial image in which the recorded performance would resonate. This is an arbitrary operation, yet it communicates, often at an unconscious level, a great deal of information. Using the QR code, try listening to the difference between a *wašənt* (flute) recorded at the time without reverberation and the restored version of the same recording with added reverberation, which introduces a spatial component into our listening.

Further comparative listenings are available via the QR codes. These examples illustrate the kinds of interventions that are possible, while also offering a tool for understanding that our listening practices are always historically conditioned.

BIOGRAPHIES OF MUSICIANS

There is a line of inquiry that urgently requires development in the coming years. It concerns the personal and collective histories of the musicians whose art is preserved in these recordings. This is the direction toward which future research should move. The reassembled archive ought to be regarded as a foundation for further study, with the hope that new documentary sources, as well as oral history records, will emerge to support it.

At present, the publication of the archive re-circulates a previously marginalised cultural heritage. However, the political and social system within which the recordings were produced - with its apparatus of coercion, segregation, and violence - still occupies a central position in the narrative. It is necessary to foreground the life experiences as well as the collective and individual trajectories of the musicians, so as to render more clearly the agency of the artists and their communities.

Although much remains to be done, in some cases we possess information about key moments in the lives of specific musicians.

Arguably the best-known performer among the recorded artists is Nəgatwa Kälkay. Nəgatwa, originally from the Wällo region, did not come from an *azmari* family, yet she possessed notable vocal talent and a timbre that remains recognisable in the recordings. In various interviews in the following decades, she described her life under Italian occupation, noting that her participation in those recording sessions served, for her, as a means of sending a message of hope to all Ethiopians compelled to endure that regime. She also emphasised her agency in selecting the repertoire and in employing the wax and gold (*sämənna wärq*) strategy, embedding layered meanings within ostensibly straightforward texts. She remained highly active after the return of the *nəguś*, but withdrew from professional artistic life after a few years. Nevertheless, she continued to be a respected public figure and was awarded a honorary doctorate by Addis Ababa University.

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MORE ABOUT THE MUSICIANS AND
LISTEN TO THEIR MUSIC

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Färädä Gola was a *mäsinqo* player and singer. Already recognised as an *azmari* during the Italian period, he became a central figure at the Hagär Fəqr Tiyatər - an institution established by the Emperor in a former Italian military building to foster a sense of national unity tested by the years of occupation. Nəgatwa also belonged to Hagär Fəqr Tiyatər for some years. Färädä recorded a number of discs for the Checchia collection, often in collaboration with other musicians and singers.

Some of the most valuable recordings document the *bägāna* repertory and performers - Dämse Dästa, ato Wäldä Maryam, Gəbräsəllase Täsəmma - of the period. Scholars and practitioners of the instrument attach great importance to knowing the names, lives, and music of the artists who preceded them. Moreover, because the *bägāna* is a devotional instrument, the recorded songs represent not only artistic creations but, above all, acts of devotion that continue to inspire listeners and musicians today.

RECORDED INSTRUMENTS

These historical recordings offer sonic portraits of several instruments that continue to hold significant roles in the musical practices of the Horn of Africa.

- *Mäsinqo*. The one-string traditional fiddle is the most recorded instrument of the collections of the 1930s. Emblematic of the performance practices of the *azmariwočč*, it accompanies many documented songs. Its distinctive, penetrating timbre - largely shaped by the left hand's stopping and pressure on the single string - was captured with some difficulties by the recording technologies of the period.
- *Kərar*. A bowl lyre, typically with five to six strings. It is plucked or strummed with the fingers or a plectrum and serves both as an accompaniment to voice and other instruments and as the main instrument in dance repertoires. In recent decades, the *kərar* has evolved to incorporate metal tuning machines and, in some cases, magnetic pickups adapted from electric guitars.
- *Käbäro*. It is a double-handed drum with a conical shape. The musician usually carries it with a band over the shoulder, so that it can be played with both hands. Ubiquitous in Eritrean and Ethiopian Orthodox processions, it is audible in the religious recordings made in the 1930s.

- *Bägäna* ("Harp of David"). A ten-string box lyre used for devotional (though not strictly liturgical) performance. It is larger than the *kərar*. In the recordings of the 1930s, a single performer sings while accompanying his voice on the instrument. Contemporary practices favours the same approach.
- *Wašənt*. An end-blown flute with finger holes, made of reed, wood, or bamboo. Originally associated with shepherds, it also assumes important roles in larger ensembles. Performers employ extensive ornamentation, which has made the instrument well suited to urban and contemporary idioms.
- *Mələkkət*. A straight natural trumpet fashioned from wood or metal. In these recordings, it appears in ensemble contexts alongside the *käbäro* and other instruments.
- *Əmbilta*. An end-blown flute without finger holes. Players vary the position of the mouth, to produce the fundamental and its overtones, and it is commonly performed in ensembles to create interlocking (hocketed) melodic lines.
- *'əlləta*. A high-pitched vocal ululation, clearly audible in some recordings, produced to express joy at ceremonies and communal celebrations. It is a vocal practice traditionally performed by women.

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SCAN THE QR CODE AND EXPLORE MORE ABOUT THE INSTRUMENTS AND LISTEN TO THEIR SOUNDS

THE “UFFICIO STAMPA E PROPAGANDA”

A crucial role in organising the recordings was played by the Ufficio Stampa e Propaganda of the Governatorato Centrale dell’Africa Orientale Italiana. As part of the Ufficio Politico (Political Office), the Ufficio Stampa (Press Office) had, from the time of General Pietro Badoglio’s troops entering Addis Ababa, exercised control over and managed the flow of information. For example, it supervised and approved film footage produced by the Istituto Luce or by other companies.

All the records in the Columbia collection bear the stamp of the Ufficio Politico. It is likely that the stamp signified a form of approval for the recorded pieces and the themes addressed by the performers. Another possibility is that the stamp indicated a form of ownership, and that the extant copies are precisely those held by the Ufficio Stampa. It is noteworthy that multiple copies of two titles (discs catalogued as A.I. 605 and 620) have been located, all stored together in a private depot. It is probable that the Ufficio Stampa held promotional copies of the recordings, either for internal use or for distribution on official occasions. However, further clarification is still needed on this point.

In a covering letter dated 4 March 1940, the then director of the Ufficio Stampa e Propaganda, Ugo Bordoni, sent to Ugo Giglio, then director of the Museo dell’Africa italiana (Museum of Italian Africa, 1937-1947), several copies of discs recorded in Ethiopia. In this letter, Bordoni did not mention the record label; he merely identified the discs by their serial numbers. From these numbers, it can be determined that they were not part of the Columbia collection but were issued by other record companies (primarily Parlophon).

In the letter, Bordoni stipulated the terms for using these recordings: “they may be used exclusively for reasons of study and not otherwise, because their content, as can be seen from the summary provided for each of them, is an exaltation of the former Negus and of the ancient rulers of Ethiopia.” One of the discs sent to the Museum of Italian Africa in Rome contained a recording of an ecclesiastical chant sung in Ge’ez, the ancient language preserved in the liturgy of the Ethiopian Orthodox Tewahedo Church. Another - accessible via the QR code - is a recording of a traditional chant of incitement and preparation

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for battle, performed by two artists identified as *ato* Täkile Mängästu and *ato* Moga (reported in the Odeon Collection as *ato* Tachaele Mangistou and *ato* Mogha). The letter indicated the kinds of control and censorship exercised by the Italian military and administrative apparatus over local

artistic expressions. The power of oral communication and of music was well understood, as demonstrated by the persecutions of 1937. The Fascist authorities could not allow such power to be unleashed through a gramophone recording.

SCAN THE QR CODE
AND FIND OUT MORE

PERSECUTIONS AND KILLINGS OF MUSICIANS

The violence perpetrated by the Italian army and the Blackshirts deployed throughout Ethiopian lands did not spare musicians. The most prominent musician to die at Italian hands during those years was probably Bäläw. Bäläw was known in Ethiopia and beyond for his height. Contemporary reports place him at approximately 7 feet 5 inches (about 228 cm). Chosen by the Emperor precisely because of his stature, Bäläw, at the time of the Italian invasion, led the imperial band with his imposing presence, playing the snare drum. He appears to have been executed by the Italians in May 1936, after being captured together with a group of patriots.

Assicurare con parola “indovini”

After the attempt on Viceroy Rodolfo Graziani's life on 19 February 1937 - he had been appointed to Italian East Africa in June 1936 following Pietro Badoglio's resignation - the ensuing violent reprisals targeted, among the primary victims, hermits, sorcerers, fortune-tellers, and storytellers. According to the Italian authorities, these figures “with their foolish prophecies kept the population of the capital in turmoil, or at the very least in a state of perplexity.” The central military command requested confirmation of the executions. “Ensure using the word *indovini*”, Graziani instructed.

The term “storytellers” unequivocally identified the *azmariwočč* and their activity. This is confirmed by the many photographs of *azmariwočč* preserved in Italian archives that bear the caption “cantastorie,” sometimes “cantastorie nomade” (itinerant storyteller), reflecting the strong prejudice against the role of the *azmari* in society at the time. A telegram dated 19 March 1937 stated that seventy “indovini, cantastorie e eremiti” were executed in the capital. The persecutions of the *azmariwočč* were coordinated by Colonel Aldo Princivalle, then head of the Political and Information Offices of the Governorate-General of Italian East Africa. During those months, telegrams from the commanders of the military divisions and the governors of the *governatorati* into which the empire had been partitioned converged on Princivalle's office, and it was he who compiled the tally later reported by the historian Giorgio Rochat of 1,877 executions. The figure did not distinguish between fortune-tellers, storytellers, and preachers - including religious figures - so it is impossible today to determine how many musicians were in fact executed or subjected to internment.

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One noteworthy detail is that the lists of political deportees later allowed to return to Addis Ababa in 1938 include two names - Zärihun Täsämma and Bäläy Kása (respectively reported as Zerihun Tesemma and Belay Kassa in the Columbia collection) - that also appear in the list of musicians recorded in 1939. Of course, this may be

a case of homonymy, yet it is not difficult to imagine that some of the *azmariwočč* active in Addis Ababa at the time of the recordings had encountered the most violent and repressive aspects of the Italian occupation.

In carrying out the reprisals and persecution of musicians, how were Italian soldiers to determine who posed the greater danger - who should be eliminated and who should be consigned to internal exile? The criterion was their own abilities: “the more followers they have,” the orders stated, “the more dangerous they are.”

In the image on the canvas, a photograph of Bäläw is reproduced at life size. At the centre is an image preserved at the Biblioteca IsIAO (Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Rome) bearing the caption “cantastorie nomade” (itinerant storyteller).

— THE GETTYSBURG TIMES, MONDAY, MAY 18, 1936 — ***Giant Royal Umbrella Bearer Of Haile Selassie Is Executed***

Addis Ababa, May 18 (AP). — A giant former umbrella carrier for Emperor Haile Selassie, said to be the tallest man in Ethiopia, was executed Sunday by an Italian firing squad.

The execution followed a number of others and the expulsion of four journalists from Ethiopia. It was officially stated that the death sentences were solely for murder in the act of pillage and looting.

Newspaper men deserted from the country were accused of “anti-Italian activities and espionage.” They were George Steer, correspondent for the London Times and the New York Times; Isadore Nebenzahl, a representative of the Havas (French) news agency; Alceos Anapolo, a Hearst correspondent, and M. D. Robillard, director of an Ethiopian newspaper. Many others were expected to follow.

Those expelled left Saturday morning on a train for Djibouti.

The emperor's former umbrella carrier, Balahu, was condemned by a military tribunal on charges of “espionage and brigandage.”

The towering man, who was 7 feet 5 inches in height, became at one time a drum major in the Imperial Band. The emperor discovered him in 1934 when he presided over the supreme court, where Balahu was on trial for the murder of a rival in a love affair.

The emperor was so impressed that he paid “blood money” on behalf of Balahu and made him official umbrella carrier.

When the war broke out he transferred him to the imperial band.

A SELECTION OF RECORDS

This section of the exhibition introduces visitors to the 78 rpm shellac records that preserved this musical heritage and allowed its reconstruction. Through full-scale reproductions, it becomes clear that these discs are not only a musical medium but also objects of material culture.

Despite their relatively high cost, records became part of the everyday lives of many people, both in Italy and in the Horn of Africa. In Addis Ababa, records could be purchased at least from the 1920s onward. Sales of both musical instruments and records increased during the years of the Italian occupation, as evidenced by advertisements in the press. The ads reproduced here promote the sale of 78 rpm recordings made by *näggadras* Täsämma Ešäte in Germany in 1910 and released by Odeon (today accessible in cd format thanks to Wolfgang Bender's research and the re-release on the no. 27 of the *Éthiopiennes* series).

The earliest advertisement identified to date is dated 1920 in the Ethiopian calendar (1927–1928 in the Gregorian calendar).

Shellac 78s were bought, kept, and sometimes taken on journeys. They could be listened to at home, provided one had a gramophone or a combined radio-gramophone set. They also lent themselves to shared listening in

public spaces, and they featured in radio broadcasts.

The reproductions on display here allow visitors to experience this materiality directly, as it was inseparable from the sonic content preserved in the grooves of the discs. What is presented is a small selection of the discs

identified, catalogued, and digitised, intended to offer as broad an overview as possible of the variety of recordings, places of origin, and documented contexts. The QR code on the flip side of each reproduced disc provides access to the original track in restored version, with an effort to retain the sonic character as it can still be heard from the shellac record itself.

The QR code displayed alongside provides access to the complete catalogue of digitised recordings of music in the Horn of Africa in the 1930s.

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UDITE I VOSTRI DISCHI SU STRUMENTI ORIGINALI

“La Voce del Padrone,”
LA MARCA DI ALTA CLASSE

Rappresentante esclusiva per l'Etiopia:
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PARSEGHIAN A. - Corso Vittorio Emanuele, 146

ዓለም ሰቅ ሲኒ ንይነት የተሰማ አገሪቱ ሙዚቃ ሸክላ ይገኛል። ሙዚቃም በየ ንድፍ ነቱ እንደ ሌንጅር ቤት በዱቤ ለመሸጥ ይቻላል። ሌንጅር (PHENIX) የአጅ ወርቅ ለዓትና የኪስ ወርቅ ለዓት ይገኛል።

ALEM

የ ወርቅ ለዓት

ODEON

የምንፈልገው ሁሉ ወደ ዓለም ቤት ይገኛል ኒካላ።

RESTITUTION OF THE SOUND ARCHIVE

The fundamental aim of the research presented here is to bring to scholarly and public attention a dispersed archive. A complete copy of the materials assembled has been donated to the Ethiopian national archive in Addis Ababa (National Archive and Library Agency) where it will be available for consultation. The research team has also initiated discussions with additional institutions to identify further appropriate sites for preservation and access.

Over the past several years, fundamental ethical and political issues have come to the foreground in music studies, particularly in ethnomusicology. The main questions are: to whom do recordings and audiovisual materials belong when they were collected in distant lands and communities but are held in libraries and universities elsewhere? And who determines the appropriate uses of these materials?

The debate has increasingly centred on “musical repatriation.” The term “repatriation” draws on initiatives undertaken by some European and North American museums - often in collaboration with local leaders and indigenous activists - to return cultural artifacts and works of art to their communities of origin. Audio and audiovisual archives raise questions that are, in

some respects, even more complex, since they comprise collections that have fixed living traditions in time, conserved the voices of existing individuals, and document practices that can still be heard and observed today. To highlight these specific issues, other terms - such as “rematriation” and “re-activation” - have been proposed. Nevertheless, the need to undertake restitution projects remains pressing.

The possibilities afforded by digitisation and the internet are compelling. At the same time, they introduce dilemmas of their own: first, online availability does not guarantee unrestrained access for people everywhere; second, once musical creations, sounds, and recorded voices are placed online, they may be subject to re-uses that might not be in line with values of the communities concerned. Some re-uses might even jeopardise them.

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DIGNITY RESTORATION

Building on Bernadette Atuahene’s theorisation, this restitution initiative has aimed not only to return the archive but also to address what she defines as “dignity takings.” The production of recordings under conditions of occupation - where the levers of decision-making and production were controlled by an occupying force that often exhibited overt violence toward local musicians -

constitutes, beyond the appropriation of material goods, a dignity taking. Any restitution effort therefore has a duty to acknowledge this history and to ask how a process of “dignity restoration” can be initiated. By situating the sonic creations in their context and making their documentation available to a wider audience, this exhibition is intended as an initial step in that direction.

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Curators Andemta Collective; Gianpaolo Chiriaco; Valentina Fusari

Online platform design Alessandra Ferlito

QR codes Tiziana Pasciuto

Research assistant Eden Solomon

Additional research assistants Tamirat Alemayehu Gebremariam; Gioia Toscani De Col

Digitisation Eden Solomon; Endrias Teklu; Gianpaolo Chiriaco; unnamed contributors

Collectors and sellers involved in the research Abdi Negash Hassen; Carlo Iori; Endrias Teklu; Munib Shemsu; unnamed collectors

Sound restoration and editing Carlo Nardi

Graphic design Leonardo Laviano

Images

- Presentation: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, scioa-20-a-05
- Italian Colonialism in Africa: La Domenica del Corriere, Anno 1 n. 43, 20 October 1899, p. 1
- Italy and Ethiopia: Istituto Geografico Militare, Firenze, 1936
- The Exotic Sound: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Amara-20-a-14
- The Musical Context: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Amara-20-a-15 and Amara-20-a-02
- Persecutions and Killings of Musicians: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Eritrea-20-a-1-iv-01
- The Ufficio Stampa e Propaganda: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, scioa-20-a-02
- The Digital Archive: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, scioa-20-a-01
- Recorded Instruments: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Galla e Sidama-19-a-10
- Biographies of Musicians: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Eritrea-20-a-1-iv-02
- The Checchia Collection: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Gli Annali dell’Africa Italiana, 2 (4), p. 641
- Restitution of the Sound Archive: Eritrea-20-a-1-iv-04
- A Selection of Records: Courtesy of Andemta Collective and Corriere dell’Impero, 61, 12 March 1939, p. 6
- Canvas: Courtesy of Andemta and Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, Eritrea-20-a-1-iv-03
- On this panel: Fototeca Museo dell’Africa Italiana, Biblioteca IsIAO, scioa-20-a-04

Websites

<https://afrovocality.com/category/soniethio/>

<https://redmix.eu/>

